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Research Article

Vasodilation Activity of *Saaranai Chooranam* in Experimental Rats (*In Vivo*) In the Management of *Raththa Kothippu* (Systemic Hypertension)

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ABSTRACT

Siddha Medicine is a one of the most popular medicines in nowadays, it has so many drugs using complete cure of the particular diseases. The trial drug *Saaranai chooranam* has been mentioned in siddha literature of “*Agasthiyar erandayiram – Part-III*” for the management of *Raththa kothippu* (Systemic hypertension). Primary objective of study to evaluate the Vaso dialation activity of *Saaranai chooranam* in experimental rats. This Observational in vivo study carried out Arulmigu Kalasalingam College of Pharmacy, Tamil Nadu, India. The trial drug contains equal ratio of *Saaranai* Root and *Inthuppu*, with adjuvant Ghee or Jagarry. Vasodilation drugs frequently used to treat Systemic Hypertension. A decrease in both diastolic and systolic pressures was observed after *Saaranai Chooranam* at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg. The hypotensive response to *Saaranai Chooranam* could be mediated not only by a central effect but also by a direct effect on the vessels. Effects of *Saaranai Chooranam* on blood pressure investigated whether it would interfere with the arterial blood pressure of Wistar rats. Rapid and transitory reductions of systolic and diastolic pressures were observed in at doses higher than 100 mg/kg, shows a typical recording of arterial blood pressure before and after treatment of drugs 200 and 400 mg/kg of *Saaranai Chooranam*. Systolic and diastolic pressures were significantly reduced respectively. Our results suggest that *Saaranai Chooranam* probably is responsible for the vasodilator activity.

INTRODUCTION

Today's, one of the most prevalent cardiovascular diseases between the human population mainly in developing countries is Systemic Hypertension (*Raththa kothippu*). In Siddha system of medicine

many internal medicines were prescribed for Cardiac related disorders, *Saaranai chooranam* mentioned in *Akasthiyar erandajiram Part-III* as indicated for *Raththa kothippu*, in my study I studied vasodilation activity tested by experimental rats (*In vivo*) which has been

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compared with Standard drug. Cardiovascular diseases are the main mortality cause in Sri Lanka. *Raththa Kothippu* (Systemic Hypertension) is characterized by blood pressure increase, related to heart effort to propel blood and the vascular resistance. WHO records shows that globally, an estimated 26% of the world's population affected hypertension.

“*Theraiyar Maruthuva Bharatam*” Says.

“*Vaathamai padaiththu Piththa vanniyai kaththu*

Setpa seethamai thudaiththu”

The quotes describe that *Vatha* is constructive in nature, *Piththa* is protective in nature and *Kabha* is destructive in nature. Generally, all systems of medicine, the combination of various herbs and minerals are used in proportion to activate *Vatha*, *Pitha*, *Kabha doshas* and bring about the needed balance of these three to the human body.

In Siddha aspect “*Eddu suvadi Noi naadal noi muthal naadal-Part-IP*”, the coartation says....

“*Noividam narampil nunmajai sentru kai vura mulaijil*

kalanthu uthiram noivura kothiththu thelivila mayakkam”

The heat in the blood vessels increases, so the blood vessels become constricted and the blood that flows naturally slows down and clots in the blood vessels, Blood boils in the blood vessels in the brain and reduces the clarity of the disease and blood circulation in the brain. There will also be obstruction in the flow of the heart. The primary function of vasodilation is to increase blood flow in the body to tissues that need it most. This is often in response to a localized need for oxygen but can occur when the tissue in question is not receiving enough glucose, lipids, or other nutrients. This disease affects people from

different ages and social ranges, and there are several attempts to minimize or prevent hypertension occurrence that, in their majority, involve adequate diet, physical exercises, and medications. Many infusions or decoctions were suggested for treatment of arterial hypertension in Siddha Medicine. Vasodilation medications that induce or start the dilating the blood vessels and are commonly applied to treat systemic hypertension (*Raththakothippu*).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1) Plant material and preparation of *Chooranam*

The required raw materials for preparation of *Saaranai chooranam* is collected from in and around of Tirunelveli and authenticated by Botanist, department of medicinal botany, Govt. Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai. The raw materials were purified and the medicine was prepared in the Govt. Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai, the adulterants and dust were removed. *Saaranai* root thoroughly washed in water and soaked in cow's milk. After that it steamed in milk. Dried and grind into the fine powder sieved and add same quantity of *Inthuppu*.

2.2) Compositions of Trial drug:

2.2.1) *Saaranai*:

Tamil name- *Saaranai*

English Name - Black pigweed/ giant pigweed

Botanical name - *Trianthema portulacastrm*

Family – Aizoaceae

Part Used – Root

2.2.2) *Inthuppu*:

Tamil name- *Inthuppu* / *Sainthalavanam*

English Name - Rock salt

Botanical name - *Sodium chloridum impura*

Part Used – Salt

2.3) Study Design and Controls:

All procedures concerning animals were carried out in an ethically proper way, by following guidelines. Experiments were also reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee. Male Wistar rats (240–300 g) were anesthetized with ether and the right carotid artery was dissected for arterial

blood pressure measurement using a calibrated pressure transducer (Statham, P022). A pair of external electrodes was placed on the chest for recording the blood pressure recorded with a polygraph (Astro- Med Grass Physiological Recorder, Mod. 7400). rats were randomly allocated to three experimental groups. Each group was treated with a *Saaranai Chooranam* or concentration at doses of 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg administered. Blood pressure was continuously recorded before and during administration of drugs

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Table: 1 Changes in blood pressure after treatment of *Saaranai Chooranam*

Drug concentration (mg/kg)	Blood Pressure (mmHg)	
	Systolic Blood Pressure	Diastolic Blood Pressure
0	130.02±0.01	100.17±2.05
100	126.15±0.33	86.08±0.77
0	124.28±0.55	94.48±2.76
200	126.37±0.16	80.69±1.34
0	126.99±0.99	94.15±1.01
400	94.52±0.28	76.03±0.19

Figure: 1 Changes in blood pressure after treatment of *Saaranai Chooranam*

The difference between the effect of different concentrations was considered statistically significant when $P < 0.05$, using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a post hoc Dunnett's test. Effects of *Saaranai Chooranam* on blood pressure investigated whether it would

interfere with the arterial blood pressure of Wistar rats. No changes in hemodynamic parameters were observed after treatment of 100 mg/kg of *Saaranai Chooranam*. The control heart rate beats/min was not significantly altered by *Saaranai Chooranam* (100 mg/kg). However, rapid and transitory

reductions of systolic and diastolic pressures were observed in at doses higher than 100 mg/kg. shows a typical recording of arterial blood pressure before and after treatment of drugs 200 and 400 mg/kg of *Saaranai Chooranam*. Systolic and diastolic pressures were significantly reduced respectively, after treatment of 200 mg/kg of *Saaranai Chooranam*. Mean arterial pressure was reduced from after administration of *Saaranai Chooranam*, 100 and 200 mg/kg, respectively. In contrast, of *Saaranai Chooranam* caused an increase in systolic and diastolic pressures, resulting in an increase in mean arterial pressure. Mean arterial pressure increased after intravenous injection of 200 and 400 mg/kg of *Saaranai Chooranam*, respectively. Also, as shown in *Saaranai Chooranam* significantly reduced systolic and mean arterial pressures with reduced on diastolic pressure.

4. DISCUSSION

A decrease in both diastolic and systolic pressures was observed after *Saaranai Chooranam* at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg. The hypotensive response to *Saaranai Chooranam* could be mediated not only by a central effect but also by a direct effect on the vessels. The reduction in systolic pressure observed after treatment of *Saaranai Chooranam* might be caused by the strong decrease in diastolic pressure and not by a direct effect on cardiac muscle. In this study, we demonstrated a clear difference in the pharmacological properties of the *Saaranai Chooranam* in the cardiovascular system in vivo experiments *Saaranai Chooranam* significantly reduced phenylephrine-evoked contractions of rat aorta in a concentration-dependent manner. In contrast *Saaranai Chooranam* produced a small, but not significant, increase in the contractile response of aortic rings with functional endothelium.

The vascular relaxation induced by *Saaranai Chooranam* was partially dependent on vascular endothelium integrity, since its activity was greater in arteries with an intact adrenergic nerve stimulation because *Saaranai Chooranam* inhibits noradrenaline re-uptake and increases its efflux.

5. CONCLUSION:

The current study showed that Siddha formulation *Saaranai Chooranam* had beneficial role in the management of *Raththa kothippu* because of its *in vivo* study of Vasodilator activity. Siddha interventions had better outcomes in quality of life and less side effects.

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